

Edge computing and sustainability

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Thanks to Patricia Lago for using her presentation material

Agenda

- Round of introduction (30 sec per person)
- Introduction on sustainability (5 min)
- Presentation of the conceptual framework (5 min)
- Discussion (1 h 30 min)

Round of introductions (30 sec p.p.)

Goal of this study

- How do edge computing and sustainability relate to each other?
- In which ways is the edge computing model sustainable/unsustainable?
Identifying sustainable/unsustainable patterns.

Perspectives on sustainability

Dimensions

Image: Sustainable Cities Index

<https://tinyurl.com/y3cfecs4>

Order of effects

UN Sustainable Development Goals

<https://sdgessentials.org/why-the-world-needs-the-sdgs.html>

Conceptual framework

What makes the pattern sustainable/unsustainable?

- Social
- Environmental
- Economic

An example

What makes the pattern sustainable/unsustainable?

Economic	if the customer support is of bad quality, the <u>cloud user</u> may not be able to provide a service with high QoS in case of cloud problems, hence potentially loosing customers
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Let's discuss!

What makes the pattern sustainable/unsustainable?

- Social
- Environmental
- Economic

Anything to add?

Next steps

- We will share with you the draft of the results
- We may contact you if further clarifications are needed

Thanks a lot!
Klervie, Maël, Muriel, and Patricia

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